

Stereoselective Synthesis of Chiral γ -Hydroxy- β -methyl Methylcarbinols[†]

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A simple synthesis of chiral γ -hydroxy- β -methyl methylcarbinols **1** starting from disubstituted olefins **3** is achieved in three steps: hydroboration, oxidation and hydride reduction. In the first step, excellent regioselectivity is achieved with bulky hydroborating reagent 9-BBN, giving exclusively the 2-hydroxy product as a mixture of diastereomers which are oxidized and hydride reduction of the resulting β -methyl methyl ketones **4** with bulky reagents shows a general trend in favour of the desired *syn*-isomer. The protocol is applied successfully in the stereoselective construction of the C₂₀-C₂₆ moiety **1d** of amphidinolide **B**.

The β -methyl methylcarbinol framework, $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_3$, is present in many natural products like amphidinolide **B**¹, jaspamide² and geodiamolides³ (Fig. 1). In the synthesis of jaspamide⁴ and geodiamolides^{4b,c,5} simple *syn*-4-(hydroxymethyl)-2-pentanol (**1**; R₁, R₂, P = H; Scheme 1) was an essential intermediate which was prepared by iodolactonization of chiral 2-methylpentenoic acids. This is also an important structural feature of cytotoxic macrolide amphidinolide **B** whose total synthesis is not yet achieved.

found to adopt conformation **A** (Fig. 2) where the allylic C–H is eclipsing the double bond favouring the attack on it from the less hindered side of M⁷. Fig. 2 also shows the energy-minimized structures of conformer **A** and conformer **B** of olefin **Z-3b** where the former is stabler by 0.9 kcal mol⁻¹ favouring the formation of *syn*-product. Regio- and stereoselectivity in the hydroboration of allylsilanes have been studied in detail⁸. In the hydroboration of 1,2-disubstituted olefins with alkyl substituents on one of their al-

Fig. 1

Herein, we report a synthesis of the *syn*-isomer **1** of this unique structural entity⁶, using various disubstituted olefins **3** as starting materials, in three steps (Scheme 1): regioselective hydroboration, oxidation, followed by diastereoselective hydride reduction. The final products were obtained with excellent diastereoselectivities for substrates having sterically hindered substituents at the β -carbon.

Results and Discussion

Functionalization of a double bond with a stereocenter at its allylic position is governed by 1,3-allylic strain and excellent π -facial selectivity is observed in many cases specially when it is a *cis*-double bond which forces the com-

Scheme 1. Diastereoselective synthesis of *syn*- γ -hydroxy- β -methyl methylcarbinols **1**.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Fig. 2. Energy-minimized structures of conformers A and B of olefin Z-3b.

lylic positions, bulky hydroborating reagents have shown excellent regioselectivity⁹.

Our aim in the first step was to achieve cent percent regioselectivity in the hydroboration of disubstituted olefins 3¹⁰ to get only the 2-hydroxy products. Different hydroborating reagents were tried for this purpose. Hydroboration with $\text{BH}_3 \cdot \text{THF}$ gave, after oxidative work-up, equal amounts of the two regioisomers, each as a mixture of two diastereomers. Reaction with catechol borane- $\text{Rh}(\text{I})$ (cat.) was also not successful. With IPcBH_2 ¹¹ and IPC_2BH ¹², reactions were very sluggish and did not go to completion even after prolonged reaction time.

Finally exclusive regioselectivity was achieved as desired using bulky reagent 9-BBN⁹ which led to the formation of the targetted 2-hydroxy compounds in excellent yields as a mixture of diastereomers having the *anti*-product 2 in slight excess in all the cases studied. In none of the cases studied, any 3-hydroxy product was formed with 9-BBN.

Formation of the *anti*-isomer 2 as the major product in this hydroboration step was surprising since according to the steric model A, the attack on the double bond from the less hindered side of M, which is methyl group in all our substrates, should have favoured the formation of the *syn*-product 1. Moreover, the failure of the *trans*-olefin E-3b to deliver the expected reversal of product-ratio in favour of the stereoisomer opposite to what is obtained with the *cis*-olefin Z-3b, a trend commonly observed in similar studies^{7,8}, puts in doubt the possibility of reaction going via conformer A. Maybe the β -alkoxy substituents have some chelating effect leading the reaction through an altogether different mechanism.

Attempts were then made to obtain the expected *syn*-

isomer 1 as the major product with increased selectivity by subjecting the mixture of isomers to a simple oxidation-reduction sequence. Accordingly, the diastereomeric mixture of 2-hydroxy compounds was oxidized with pyridinium dichromate (PDC) to the corresponding methyl ketones 4 in quantitative yields.

After the early reports of Leitereg and Cram¹³ and Brieme *et al.*¹⁴, not much work was done to investigate the diastereoselective nucleophilic addition to β -alkyl-substituted methyl ketones. Whereas a recent work by Nakada *et al.*¹⁵ reported excellent diastereoselectivity in the addition of various organometallics to β -methyl acylsilanes, Fleming's report on the reduction of a β -silyl methyl ketone with NaBH_4 showed only moderate diastereoselectivity⁸. In connection with his work on 1,3-asymmetric induction in hydride addition reactions to β -alkoxy substituted ketones, Evans¹⁶ mentioned about the effectiveness of sterically demanding borohydride reagents in achieving comparable, albeit little less, diastereoselection with a β -alkyl substituted isopropyl ketone. We corroborate his finding with our work on the diastereoselective reduction of β -methyl methyl ketones 4a-d.

Reductions of these β -methyl methyl ketones were then tried with three different borohydride reagents, NaBH_4 , lithium triisiamylborohydride and 9-BBN. Whereas NaBH_4 , as expected, did not show any selectivity, the other two bulky reagents exhibited the anticipated diastereoselectivity specially with substrates 4b-d having sterically hindered substituents at the β -carbon. The best reagent for this step was found to be 9-BBN which showed very good selectivity ($\sim 9 : 1$) with 4d. The overall yields in three steps and diastereoselectivities achieved using 9-BBN are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS OF 1 FROM 3 IN THREE STEPS^a

Sl. no.	Olefin 3	Products after 3 steps (Diastereomeric ratio) ^b	Overall yield (%) ^c
1.	Z-3a	1a + 2a (1 : 1)	85
2.	Z-3b	1b + 2b (3 : 1)	82
3.	E-3b	1b + 2b (3 : 1)	82
4.	Z-3c	1c + 2c (4 : 1)	80
5.	Z-3d	1d + 2d (9 : 1)	88

^a $\text{R}_1, \text{R}_2 = \text{H}, \text{P} = \text{TBDPS}$; ^b $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CH}_2\text{OBn}, \text{R}_2 = \text{H}, \text{P} = \text{TIPS}$; ^c $\text{R}_1, \text{R}_2 = \text{Me}, \text{P} = \text{TIPS}$; ^d $\text{R}_1 = \text{syn-EtOC(O)CH(OTIPS)-}, \text{R}_2 = \text{H}, \text{P} = \text{TIPS}$.

^aFirst step was regioselective hydroboration with 9-BBN followed by PDC oxidation and finally in the third step diastereoselective hydride reduction with 9-BBN.

^bRatios were determined by ¹H nmr.

^cYields refer to isolated yields of mixtures of diastereomers.

The diastereoselection can be explained by Felkin's staggered transition state model¹⁶ which explains the ob-

Fig. 3

served π -facial selectivity in this noncholate-controlled reduction of β -methyl methyl ketones. According to this model, in the transition state the β -carbon occupies a position perpendicular to the carbonyl with the largest β -substituent R_L staying away from the carbonyl (Fig. 3). The hydride attack takes place antiperiplanar to the β -carbon. The steric interactions between the methylketomethyl and β -methyl favours transition structure A over B leading to the formation of 1 as the major product. This explains why with sterically demanding R_L the diastereoselectivity excels.

The stereochemistries of the products were determined by chemical methods and detailed NMR studies, specially of **1b** and **2b** which were easily separated by standard silica gel column chromatography. First, we were interested to find out whether it was possible or not to ascertain the stereochemistries of the products from the ^1H nmr of their acyclic forms. For the *anti*-product **2b**, the two methylene protons at 3-position, H_β and H_α showed very similar splitting patterns (Fig. 4). For the *syn*-product **1b**, the coupling constants for these two protons were very different. The two methylene protons for **1a** also showed similar splittings (H_β : δ 1.5, ddd, J 14.2, 9.4 and 6.5 Hz; H_α : δ 1.23, ddd, J 14.2, 6.8 and 3.1 Hz) as they were for **1b**. For **2a**, one of the methylene protons came at δ 1.31 as ddd with 13, 10 and 5.5 Hz couplings and the other one appeared at δ 1.76 as ddd with 13, 8.1, and 2.5 Hz couplings.

Fig. 4

Subsequently, **1b** and **2b** were separately converted into their corresponding lactols **5** and **6** respectively (Scheme 2). The lactol **6** obtained from the *anti*-product **2b** (slower running in the tlc) showed NOE between 4H and 2-methyl as determined by its NOESY spectrum. The stereochemis-

Scheme 2. Synthesis of lactols **5** and **6** from **1b** and **2b** respectively. Reagents and conditions: (i) HF-Py, THF, (ii) H_2 , Pd-C, MeOH, (iii) NaO_4 , THF- H_2O (1 : 1), 90% overall.

tries were further confirmed by comparing the nmr of the products of Scheme 2 with those of the authentic samples prepared according to Scheme 3^{17,18}. The relative stereochemistries of **9** and **10** are known from the literature¹⁸. The stereochemistry of **1d** was also confirmed by converting it to the known lactol **5** in two steps: desilylation with HF-Py followed by oxidative cleavage of the resulting diol with sodium periodate.

The minor isomers in the all the cases studied could be separated easily making it a very practical method for the synthesis of chiral *syn*- β -methyl methylcarbinols **1** specially when its γ -position is sterically hindered. In case of **1d**, the newly generated hydroxyl was protected as triethylsilyl (TES) ether to have a better separation. The resulting TES-protected compound **1d** has already been used by us in the synthesis of the top-half of amphidinolide B¹⁹. The protocol will find useful applications in the synthesis of many other natural products.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of **5** and **6** from **7**. Reagents and conditions: (i) Ref. 17, (ii) I_2 , CH_3CN (Ref. 18), (iii) Bu_3SnH , AIBN, toluene, reflux, (iv) DIBAL, hexane, -78° , 78% from **9** (or **10**).

Experimental

Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian Gemini 200 or Unity 400 instrument with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard, ir spectra on Shimadzu IR-470 and Perkin-Elmer 283 B instruments and mass spectra on VG MICROMASS 70-70H and VG Auto Spec M spectrometers under electron impact (EI), chemical ionization (CI) or liquid secondary ion mass spectrometric (LSIMS) techniques.

All reactions were monitored by tlc carried out on 0.25 mm silica gel (E. Merck) plates (60F-254) with uv light, I_2 , 7% ethanolic phosphomolybdic acid-heat and 2.5%

ethanolic anisaldehyde (with 1% AcOH and 3.3% conc. H_2SO_4)-heat as developing agents. Silica gel finer than 200 mesh (Acme) was used for flash column chromatography. All reactions were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere with dry, freshly distilled solvents under anhydrous conditions unless otherwise noted. Yields refer to chromatographically and spectroscopically homogeneous materials unless otherwise stated.

General procedure for the conversion of 3 to 1: In a typical experiment, olefin 3 was treated with 9-BBN (2 equiv.) in dry THF for 16–20 h at room temperature and oxidative workups were done by sequential addition of MeOH (4 equiv.), 3 N aq. NaOH (2.2 equiv.) and 30% H_2O_2 (6 equiv.) at 0° followed by warming to 60° for 2 h^{11b}. After chromatography, the diastereomeric mixture of methyl-carbinols was oxidized with PDC (2 equiv.) in CH_2Cl_2 at room temp. for 2 h, diluted with dry ether and passed through a short pad of silica gel. The crude product was reduced with 9-BBN (1.5 equiv.) in dry THF at 0° and the workup was done in the same way as the oxidative workup described above for the hydroboration step. Products were purified by standard silica gel column chromatography: **1a**, $R_f = 0.3$ (silica gel, 10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); ν_{max} (neat) 3381, 2930, 2856, 1427, 1111, 823, 702, 613 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$, 400 MHz) δ 7.68–7.34 (10H, m, ArH), 3.88 (1H, m, CHOH), 3.48 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_2OSi), 2.4 (1H, br s, OH), 1.82 (1H, m, CHMe), 1.5 (1H, ddd, J 14.2, 9.4 and 6.5 Hz, C3-H), 1.33 (1H, ddd, J 14.2, 6.8 and 3.1 Hz, C3-H'), 1.2 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, CH_3), 1.05 (9H, s, tBu), 0.88 (3H, d, J 6.7 Hz, CH_3); **1b**, $R_f = 0.3$ (silica gel, 10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$, 400 MHz) δ 7.2–7.35 (5H, m, ArH), 4.46 (2H, Abq, OCH_2Ph), 3.94 (1H, m, CHOTIPS), 3.82 (1H, m, CHOH), 3.51 (2H, m, CH_2OBn), 3.2 (1H, br s, OH), 1.95 (1H, m, $CHCH_3$), 1.47 (1H, ddd, J 14.5, 9.6 and 8.0 Hz, C3-H), 1.32 (1H, ddd, J 14.5, 5.85 and 2.15 Hz, C3-H'), 1.18 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, CH_3), 1.1 (21H, m, TIPS), 0.96 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, CH_3); **1c**, $R_f = 0.4$ (silica gel, 10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); $[\alpha]_D^{22} = -22.2^\circ$ (c 1.0, $CHCl_3$); ν_{max} (neat) 3371, 2968, 2868, 1464, 1383, 1159, 1045, 883 and 677 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$, 400 MHz) δ 3.83 (1H, m, CHOH), 1.71 (2H, m, $CHCH_3$, C3-H), 1.2 (6H, two d, J 6.5 Hz, Me), 1.08 (1H, m, C3-H'), 1.06 (24H, m, CH_3 and TIPS), 0.94 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$, 50 MHz) δ 75.7, 66.1, 41.7, 27.7, 26.9, 24.8, 18.5, 14.9, 13.5; LSIMS m/z (%) 303 (26) [$M^+ + H$], 215 (34), 129 (60), 111 (100); **TES-protected derivative of 1d**, $R_f = 0.5$ (silica gel, 10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); $[\alpha]_D^{22} = -19.0^\circ$ (c 1.0, $CHCl_3$); ν_{max} (neat) 2945, 1751, 1464, 1383, 1240, 1140, 1014, 883, 744 and 679 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$, 200 MHz) δ 4.38

(1H, d, J 6.8 Hz, $CH(OTIPS)CO_2Et$), 4.2–4.0 (2H, m, $CO_2CH_2CH_3$), 3.94–3.76 (2H, m, CHOSi), 2.2 (1H, m, $CHCH_3$), 1.75–1.3 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.25 (3H, t, J 6.8 Hz, $CO_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.14 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, CH_3), 1.1 and 1.05 (42H, two s, TIPS), 0.94 (9H, t, J 7.8 Hz, $SiCH_2CH_3$), 0.8 (3H, d, J 6.7 Hz, CH_3), 0.56 (6H, q, J 7.8 Hz, $SiCH_2CH_3$); ^{13}C nmr ($CDCl_3$, 50 MHz) δ 172.5, 79.2, 74.9, 66.2, 60.4, 45.6, 30.6, 24.6, 18.2, 17.9, 14.2, 14.1, 13.0, 12.4, 6.9, 5.2; LSIMS m/z (%) 603 (36) [$M^+ + H - CO_2$], 401 (22), 255 (95), 157 (60), 115 (100).

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finally Wittig olefination gave Z-3a. Opening of Z-4-benzyloxy-2,3-epoxy-1-butanol with Me₂CuLi, selective protection of primary hydroxy as TBS, secondary hydroxy as TIPS, selective deprotection of primary hydroxy, Swern oxidation and finally Wittig olefination gave Z-3b, whereas the aldehyde from Swern oxidation step was converted to E-3b in three steps : CBr₄/Ph₃P, ⁿBuLi/Mel, and finally LAH reduction to E-double bond. TBDPS-protection of methyl 3-hydroxy-2-methylpropionate, treatment with MeMgI, TIPS-protection of the resulting tertiary alcohol, TBDPS-deprotection, Swern oxidation and finally Wittig olefination gave Z-3c. For the synthesis of Z-3d see Ref. 19.

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